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Analysis of the spatial structure of a pinewood phytocoenosis on basis of ecological indicators

Key words: pine forest, herb layer, spatial structure, ecological indicators

Introduction

The spatial structure of plant communities depends (among others) on ecological processes inside the community. Both habitat and biotic factors play important role in these processes. Every species composing the plant community reacts individually to environmental changes and its presence in phytocoenosis indicates proper ecological conditions for this species (LAVRENKO, KORČAGIN, ed. 1976). The dependence species-environment allows description of spatial structure of plant communities and their particular layers by use of ecological indicators (ELLENBERG et al., 1992; KOZŁOWSKA, 1991; van der MAAREL, WERGER, 1990; TER BRAAK, GREMMEN, 1987).

The present paper is an attempt to describe the spatial structure of the herb layer of a pinewood community using ecological indicator values and to reveal possible correlations between particular indicators and floristic differentiation which is analysed in other paper.

Study area and methods

The investigated phytocoenosis is located in Kraków-Częstochowa Upland, near Olkusz (Fig. 1). Phytosociologically, it belongs to the *Leucobryo-Pinetum* association (WIKA, 1982). The permanent plot 8 x 62 m was divided into 496 quadrats 1 m² each. In every quadrat all vascular plant species were noted. Next, the mean values for light (*L*), moisture (*F*), acidity (*R*) and nitrogen availability (*N*) were calculated for each quadrat using Mulva-4 computer program (WILDI, ORLOCI, 1990). Indicator values for the occurring species were taken from ELLENBERG et al. (1992), ZARZYCKI (1984) and FRANK et al. (1988). Their basic statistics is presented in Table 1 and Fig 2. The cartograms (Figs 3–6) show the spatial distribution of these values. Next, the correlations between particular ecological indicators were calculated (Fig. 7).

Fig. 1. A schematic map of investigated area:
1 – study plot

Results and discussion

The values of moisture (*F*) indicator range from 3.0 to 6.0 with mean value 4.3 (Table 1). Most values are grouped in range 4.0–5.0 (Fig. 2). Because of this, the investigated plot is very homogenous as for moisture conditions (Fig. 3).

Table 1

Basic statistical parameters of analysed ecological indicators

Indicator	Mean	Confidence intervals		Minimum	Maximum	Variance	Standard deviation
		-95%	+95%				
F	4.3	4.3	4.3	3.0	6.0	0.09	0.31
L	5.8	5.8	5.8	5.0	6.8	0.08	0.28
R	3.2	3.2	3.2	2.0	4.5	0.24	0.49
N	2.1	2.0	2.1	1.0	3.7	0.09	0.30

Light (*L*) indicator values range from 5.0 to 6.8 with mean value 5.8. The values fitted very well the normal distribution (Fig. 2). The cartogram of the spatial distribution (Fig. 4) shows high degree of heterogeneity of the investigated plot as light conditions is concerned. Light and darker places are mixed.

Acidity (*R*) indicator values range from 2.0 to 4.5 with mean value 3.2. Their distribution also fitted well normal distribution (Fig. 2). And the spatial distribution (Fig. 5) clearly shows the heterogeneity of soil acidity conditions.

And finally, nitrogen availability (*N*) indicator values range from 1.0 to 3.7 with mean value 2.1. Most of the quadrats belong to the class 2.0–2.5 (Fig. 2). In this case the plot is quite homogenous, especially its lower part (Fig. 6).

Correlation analysis (Fig. 7) suggests possible connections between acidity of soil and nitrogen availability conditions and (not so strong, but significant statistically) correlation between moisture of soil and nitrogen availability. Small differences between histograms of indicators at Fig. 2 and Fig. 7 to result from using different ranges.

There are few papers in ecological literature devoted to the role of ecological indicators as a measure of habitat conditions in a microscale. Our results confirmed the possible role of soil acidity as a factor of heterogeneity in acidophilous communities (KIMSA, 1991). Present studies suggest also such a role for nitrogen availability. This is very important because growing anthropogenic eutrophization of pine forests could easily influenced their structure. So high value of *N* indicator could be a measure of anthropogenic degradation of pine forests. Correlation between *R* and *N* indicators confirm this statement.

Fig. 2. Histograms of values distribution of analysed ecological indicators:

F - moisture, L - light, R - acidity, N - nitrogen availability

Fig. 3. Spatial distribution of moisture (F) indicator values on investigated plot:
 1 - 3.0-3.9, 2 - 4.0-4.9, 3 - 5.0-5.9

Fig. 4. Spatial distribution of light (L) indicator values on investigated plot:
 1 - 5.0-5.4, 2 - 5.5-5.9, 3 - 6.0-6.4, 4 - 6.5-6.9

Fig. 5. Spatial distribution of acidity (R) indicator values on investigated plot:

1 - 2.0-2.9, 2 - 3.0-3.9, 3 - 4.0-4.9

Fig. 6. Spatial distribution of nitrogen availability (N) indicator values on investigated plot:

1 - 1.0-1.9, 2 - 2.0-2.9, 3 - 3.0-3.9

Fig. 7. Correlation matrix of analysed ecological indicators:

F – moisture, L – light, R – acidity, N – nitrogen availability. Correlation indices between analysed ecological indicators. Marked correlations are significant at $p < 0.05$

Conclusions

Analysis of ecological indicators values is a good way to study inner heterogeneity of the pine forest communities. This method should be used simultaneously with direct floristic analysis. This two methods, though basing on the same quantitative data, revealed different features and trends in spatial structure. There is a need for further studies in other types of plant communities to confirm suggested possibilities of ecological indicators in studies of phytocoenosis' dynamic.

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ANALIZA STRUKTURY PRZESTRZENNEJ FITOCENOZY BORU SOSNOWEGO
NA PODSTAWIE WSKAŹNIKÓW EKOLOGICZNYCH

Streszczenie

Pozioma struktura warstwy runa boru sosnowego była analizowana za pomocą wskaźników ekologicznych wilgotności (F), stosunków świetlnych (L), zasobności w azot (N) i odczynu gleby (R). Stałe poletko badawcze podzielono na 496 kwadratów o wielkości 1 m^2 . W każdym kwadracie notowano obecność roślin naczyniowych runa. Na tej podstawie dla każdego kwadratu obliczono średnie wartości badanych wskaźników ekologicznych, posługując się pakietem programów Mulva-4. Analizowano przestrzenne rozmieszczenie średnich wartości (przedstawione w postaci kartogramów) oraz korelacje pomiędzy poszczególnymi wskaźnikami. Stwierdzono, że wskaźniki pozostałe wskaźniki (wilgotności i zasobności w azot) dają bardziej homogenny obraz. Analiza korelacji sugeruje istnienie związków pomiędzy wilgotnością i zasobnością w azot, przynajmniej w odniesieniu do badanej fitocenozy.

АНАЛИЗ ПОВЕРХНОСТНОЙ СТРУКТУРЫ ФИТОЦЕНОЗА СОСНОВОГО БОРА
НА ОСНОВАНИИ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ

Резюме

Горизонтальная структура травяного покрова соснового бора проанализирована, используя экологические показатели влажности (F), световых соотношений (L), обогащенность азотом (N) и реакции почвы (R). Постоянная площадь опробования была разделена на 496 квадратов площадью 1 м^2 . В каждом квадрате отмечено присутствие сосудистых растений травяного покрова. На этом основании для каждого квадрата подсчитаны средние значения экологических показателей, пользуясь пакетом программ Mulva-4. Анализировано пространственное размещение средних значений (представленных в виде картограмм), а также корреляции между отдельными показателями. Установлено, что световые показатели и реакция почвы проявляют большую степень гетерогенности исследованной поверхности, в то время как остальные показатели (влажность и обогащение азотом) дают более хомогенную картину. Анализ корреляций предполагает существование связи между влажностью и обогащением азотом, по крайней мере по отношению к исследованному фитоценозу.

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